

SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF WOMEN PRACTICING MECHANIZED AGRO-PROCESSING IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The socio-economic status of women practicing mechanized agro processing in Nigeria was assessed. Women agro-processors were identified and selected through their various State's ADPs across the six geo-political zones in Nigeria. The data generated were basically primary and obtained through personal interview schedule with a well-structured questionnaire. Data were collected based on the socio-economic variables such as age, marital status, educational status, main occupation and household size. The data generated were subjected to descriptive statistics involving frequency count and percentage computation. From the results gathered, it was observed that majority of the respondents (42.1%) were within the age group of 41 to 50 years, while 71.1% of them were married. Result further revealed that 86.8% were educated up to tertiary level, 68.4% were operators in the agro-processing centres, while 73.68% were maintaining a household size of 5 to 10. It was concluded in this study that majority of the educated women in the study area are educated and in their active age with high level of financial burdens, which influenced their decision towards embracing the practice of agro-processing technologies as a source of livelihood.

Keywords: Socio-economic characteristics, Agro-processing, Women

1. INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, food waste represents an important global challenge, with approximately one-third of all food produced for human consumption are lost or wasted annually thereby leading to severe environmental, economic, and social consequences. The issue not only exacerbates food insecurity but also contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, waste of resources, and economic losses estimated at over \$1 trillion each year (Arowosegbe, 2024). Jeremić *et al.* (2024) reported that one-third of the total amount of food produced every year that are lost or wasted is an indication that there exist an extremely high level of inefficiency in the food supply chain.

This is the tragic reality confronting Nigeria and the human race in general. Fogel (2004) asserted a high level of food wastage by British consumers and American retailers, food services and householders. He opined that the 1.5 billion people that are hungry could be alleviated by conserving the food including the arable crops such as wheat, maize and soy fed to animals to produce the wasted meat and dairy products.

High post-harvest losses observed during production and processing of food which is due to limited food processing and preservation capacity constitute part of the major factors hindering food and nutrition security in Nigeria. Ineffective or inappropriate food processing technologies, careless harvesting and inefficient post-harvest handling practices, bad roads, bad market practices and inadequate or complete lack of storage facilities, packing houses and market infrastructures, among others, are factors responsible for high post-harvest food losses in Nigeria (Uzoejinwa1 *et al.*, 2016). The use of appropriate processing technologies and storage facilities would guarantee food security. Gernah *et al.* (2013) stated that the value of agricultural raw materials could be improved by using appropriate food processing technologies in removing unwanted materials and transforming these

raw materials into high quality finished products. When appropriate processing methods are employed, the transformed finished product has extended shelf life, higher nutritional and economic value, thus contributing to the food security concern of the populace.

FAO (1997) describes agro-processing as the transformation of products originating from agriculture, forestry, and fisheries. It encompasses global-to-local patterns (processing of imported agricultural commodities to be sold on the local market) and local-to-global patterns (processing of locally-produced commodities for export). It varies from simple preservation operations such as drying products in the sun to more complex, capital-intensive processes. www.agriculturenigeria.com/agro-processing simply defines it traditionally as the transformation of raw materials and intermediate goods derived from the agricultural sector into finished products.

Agro-processing industries are typically comprised of upstream and downstream industries. The Upstream sector of agro-processing refers to the initial processing of agricultural commodities such as rice milling, leather tanning, cotton ginning, fish canning, among others. The downstream sector of agro processing are involved in more complex processing of intermediate products made from agricultural materials and include the making of bread, biscuits, textiles, paper, clothing, footwear, etc. (FAO, 1997).

Agro-processing plays a crucial role in converting raw agricultural products into value-added goods, extends their shelf life and improves their marketability. By adding value through processing, Africa can unlock its agricultural potential, generate employment opportunities, and enhance economic development. Martorano and Gonnelli (2022) stated that agro-processing encompasses a range of activities which include sorting, grading, packaging, preserving, and transforming raw materials into finished products. The development of agro-processing centres, equipped with mills and other processing equipment, can enhance the economic feasibility of processing activities in rural areas.

Agro-processing and agro processors face significant challenges like limited value addition, administrative barriers, and inadequate linkages with marketing and financial services. The development of the sector has been hindered by technological limitations and the need for new agricultural solutions to improve productivity and quality (Thembinkosi, 2022). Agro-processing also holds significant promise for economic and social development, however, it is also confronted with some challenges that require strategic interventions. The integration of new technologies, interdisciplinary research, and supportive policies can help overcome these obstacles and unlock the full potential of agro-processing industries. This approach can lead to sustainable growth and improved livelihoods, most especially in the rural communities.

Socio-economic characteristics refers to the position of an individual or family in the society, which is central to understanding the socio-economic characteristics of farmers (Kadian and Kumar, 2002). Demographic factors such as age, gender, education level, and family size significantly influence the socio-economic characteristics of farmers. Understanding these factors helps in assessing the labour force and the potential for agricultural productivity in a region (Niemets and Lohvynova, 2017).

Women's contributions to agricultural production in Nigeria have been noted in several literatures. Among different factors, the socio-economic characteristics of the farmers influence their production-decision in agribusiness (Oyinbo *et al.*, 2019). Akinbami *et al.* (2012) asserted that the socio-economic conditions of women who participate actively in the economy of the country, particularly at the grass-roots level, have remained challenging despite implementation of economic reforms in Nigeria.

Amanze *et al.*(2023) stressed that women farmers are the most involved in off-farm agro-processing activities. They are highly involved in cassava processing into gari, tapioca, odourless fufu, into pancake and cassava flour, maize processing into pap, corn meal, processing and utilization of soybean into soya flour, soya milk etc, Others are into maize processing for the making of maize flour and malted maize-milk drink, cocoyam processing for the making of cocoyam chips and cocoyam flour. Further processing activities include plantain processing for the making of plantain chips and plantain flour.

Agro-processing, according to Quartey and Darkwa (2015), is grouped into factory agro-processing and domestic agro-processing. Domestic agro-processing is dominated by females with the characteristics of illiteracy, informal training, use of family labour, variability in the quality of processed output (Owoo and Lambon-Quayefio, 2017). Notwithstanding these, domestic agro-processing is highly important in the country as it provides livelihood support to women in rural areas (Mabe, 2022).

1.1 Empirical Review

According to Huyer (2016), agriculture is the largest employment sector for 60% of women in Oceania, Southern Asia and sub-Saharan Africa as these women makes up two-third of the world's 600 million small livestock managers. Despite this, women's activities in agriculture are characterized by a global gender gap in vulnerabilities, access to resources, and productivity. Fanelli (2022) observed at the EU level (EU-28), around 30% of agricultural farms are operated by women whereby we have one farm in five. In rural areas of EU, women represent over 50% of the rural population. In the EU's agricultural sector, women accounts for about 45% of the total working population and for about 35% of their workers. The work of female farmers accounts for 31% of the total working hours (Franić and Kovačiček, 2019).

According to Abdisa *et al.* (2024), women makes up to more than 50% of the agricultural labour force but contribute less than 30% to agricultural productivity. Agriculture is the main source of livelihood in Ethiopia which contributes more than 35% to GDP, 90% to forex earnings, and 70% to employment sources. For improving economic well-being, ensuring sustainable development, and reducing poverty will become impossible if the role of women are ignored. Mukasa and Salami (2016) posited that empowering women has become a much-discussed subject among many political leaders, civil rights activists, and women's associations. In agriculture, women particularly face daunting constraints that significantly limit their potential and enmesh them into a gender productivity trap.

The study which emphasis on the socio-economic assessment of women practicing mechanised agro-processing in Nigeria is imperative due to the important role played by women over the years in the agricultural value chain of the country and beyond, in spite of the socio-economic challenges they face as noted in several studies carried out over the years. For instance, Anderson *et al.* (2021) reported that gender inequality in agriculture has been recorded to have cost Africa several billion annually. Furthermore, women in agriculture according to Huyer (2016), lack access to essential resources which limits their productivity to a very large extent. Therefore; empowering women through the practise of mechanized agro-processing serves as an important tool for poverty reduction as observed in EU and some sub-Saharan countries (Fanelli, 2022; Mukasa and Salami, 2016). It is based on these facts that it has become necessary to access the socio-economic characteristic of women involved in agro-processing in Nigeria as a means of identifying challenges and strategies to enable women contribute fully to the agro-processing industry in Nigeria.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

The study area comprises of women agro-processors from the six geo-political zones of Nigeria. A sample size comprising of 76 women into agro-processing activities were randomly selected across the six geo-political zones using the already established Agricultural Development Centres available in the country. Upon selection, these women were assembled at the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin for a focus group discussion and filling of a structured designed questionnaire in generating data to be used for the study.

2.2 Method of Data Collection and Sampling Procedure.

The primary source of generating data which involved the use of structured questionnaire was used for this study. Data were collected based on the socio-economic variables such as age, marital status, educational status, main occupation and household size. The response of these processors forms the primary data used.

2.3 Statistical Tool

The data obtained from the 76 respondents who were into agro-processing activities in the six geo-political zone of Nigeria were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis involving frequency count and percentage computation. The SPSS statistical package of version 25.0.0.0 was used for the data computation

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Summary of Data Collated for Socio-Economic Characteristic of the Study Area

The selected related characteristics of the women practicing mechanized agro-processing in Nigeria include the use of age, marital status, level of education, occupation, household size and type of business engaged. The socio-economic characteristics of women practicing mechanized agro-processing in Nigeria is presented in Table 1. From Table 1, it was observed that 71.1% of the women under study were married, 86.8% were educated up to tertiary level, 68.4% were agro processors (machine operators) while 73.68% were maintaining a household size of 5 to 10. Table 1 further revealed that majority of the women (42.1%) were within the age group of 41 to 50 years.

Table1. Socio-Economic Characteristics of women practicing mechanized agro-processing in Nigeria

Socio-economic variable	Grouping of variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age of Respondent (Year)	21 – 30	18	23.7
	31 – 40	8	10.5
	41 – 50	32	42.1
	Above 50	18	23.7
Marital status	Single	14	18.4
	Married	54	71.1
	Widowed	8	10.5
	Divorced	0	0.0
Educational status	Quranic education	2	2.6
	Adult education	2	2.6
	Primary education	2	2.6
	Secondary education	4	5.3
	Tertiary education	66	86.8
Main Occupation	Civil Servant	2	2.6
	Agro-Processing centre operator	52	68.4

	Student	6	7.9
	Farmer	8	10.5
	Trading	8	10.5
	Others	0	0.0
Household size	1 – 4	16	21.05
	5 – 10	56	73.68
	Above 10	4	5.26

3.1.1 Age of respondents

Age is an important factor of the social-economic status of a given population. Figure 1 show that the least involved in mechanized agro-processing among women in Nigeria fell within the age group of 31 to 40 years, which represents 10.5%; while the most involved were women within the age group of 41 to 50 years.

Figure 1. Age of respondents

This low level of involvement of women within the age group of 31 to 40 years may have been attributed to several factors such as economic, cultural and religious factors. However, most women within the age group of 31 to 40 years in Nigeria are still in their child bearing state and thus may have been constrained by pregnancy or nursing infants. Cultural perception of young and newly married women engaging in such physically tasking occupations as ignoble may have contributed as well as peer influence. However, the ever-increasing socio-economic crisis such as family welfare as noted by Yahaya (2002) and Adepoju *et al.* (2007) may have forced women within the age group of 41 to 50 years into agro processing activities, as most families experience higher financial burdens with higher number of children, higher children welfare and educational demand. Age may also be a contributing factor for their choice of mechanized agro-processing. This is similar to the findings of Akinbami *et al.* (2012) while studying technology adoption and women entrepreneurial behaviour. According to the findings of Eze *et al.* (2017) and Adenugba and John (2014), respondents within the age group of 41 to 50 years had the highest level of agro-technological adoption in their study area. Figure 1 further showed that respondents within the age group of 21 to 30 years were also actively involved in mechanized agro-processing activities. It appears that most of the respondents at this age group are students of secondary and tertiary institutions who either inherited the processing centres which they operate or are part time employees in the agro-processing centres in order to assist their parents in easing the financial burden of the family.

3.1.2 Educational status

Education level is a major determinant to women agro-processors. It was observed from the study that 66 of the respondents representing 86.8% attended tertiary institution as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Educational status of the respondents

This suggests that majority of the respondents were educated, thus, understanding and adoption of mechanization technologies would not be a problem to them. Most of the respondents may have been acquainted to the limitations of traditional processing method and the merits of agro-processing technologies. This view is supported by the finding of (Eze *et al.*, 2017; Opaluwa, 2014; Audu, 2012; Adepoju *et al.*, 2007) which revealed that education is not only an important determinant in the involvement and adoption of agricultural innovation but also a tool for agricultural productivity. The rising level of graduate unemployment may have also contributed to the dominance of educated women in agro-processing; perhaps as a lucrative means of earning money for themselves.

3.1.3 Main occupation

This study revealed that majority of the respondents (52) were agro-processing centre operators, while 8 are traders and farmers each as shown in Figure 3. Respondents on government payroll (civil servants) were only 2 out of the total respondents.

Figure 3. Main occupation of the respondents

This implies that most of the respondents' main occupation involves processing of the farmer's farm produce who have no access to mechanized processing technologies. The result also implies that some of the respondents (8) who are predominantly farmers process mainly their own crops as well as commercially processing for other farmers. However, some of the respondents (especially the traders) seem to be engaged in the buying of the unprocessed farm produce from these farmers thereby processing themselves for selling in the market. This was observed during oral interview with some of the respondents. This was in agreement with the findings of Eze *et al.* (2017 while assessing the socio-economic characteristics of melon processors who are into the use of motorized melon shellers in Edu Local Government Area of Kwara State, Nigeria. Majority of the processors who were traders buy unshelled melon from farmers who by this process shell them for sale.

3.1.4 Household size

This study shows that 56 of the respondents had a house hold size of 5 to 10 persons while 16 of the respondents has a household size of 1 to 4 persons as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Household size of the respondents

This implies that majority of the respondents maintain a very large family size. Having a serious economic burden, they therefore find the need to empower the family members through agro-processing business venture. Other researchers such as (Eze *et al.*, 2017; Ajani, 2011; Enwelu, 2011; Emodi, 2009?) in their respective findings, observed that households in Nigeria are characterized by large family size with high dependency ratio.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusion

The study showcased the impact of the socio-economic characteristics of women practicing mechanized agro-processing. Majority of the participating women in the agro processing centres were married, educated and within the age group of 41 to 50 years.

The study highlights that the participation of women in agro-processing activities proves their economic importance in income generation to the agricultural value chain. However, younger women face lots of barriers stemming from cultural and economic constraints, as well as the demands of childbearing and childcare.

Priority should be placed on younger women who wish to venture into agro-processing value chain system, so as to effectively harness their young and vibrant energy into the sector. This is because agricultural mechanization has the capacity for women empowerment, providing opportunities for

income diversification and self-employment. Doing so will act as a catalyst for enhancing women's livelihoods and driving sustainable agricultural development in Nigeria.

4.2 Recommendations

Following the findings in this study, it is recommended that:

1. Strategic policies aimed at encouraging younger women within the age group of 31-40 years to participate in mechanized agro-processing should be enacted and promoted.
2. Further studies should be conducted to evaluate the awareness and gender friendliness of conventional agro-processing technologies in Nigeria.

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